

Building Gaps: Parental Involvement in Students' Achievements

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Abstract. Parental involvement in education plays a crucial role in shaping students' achievement and personal success. This study examined the role of parental involvement in student achievement from the perspectives of teachers in Banaybanay Elementary School, focusing on the unique cultural and socioeconomic factors that influence parental involvement in the Philippines. The study explored teachers' experiences in bridging gaps in students' achievements, coping mechanisms in promoting student achievement, and educational management insights drawn from the findings. Employing a qualitative phenomenological research design, interviews and surveys were conducted with teachers to gain insights into the current state of parental involvement in the school. Thematic analysis revealed that teachers recognized the positive impact of parental involvement on academic performance and attitudes toward learning. They employed effective communication, collaboration, workshops, and leveraging technology to overcome challenges. The findings highlighted the importance of fostering effective communication and collaboration between teachers and parents and the need for collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility among all stakeholders. The study provided valuable educational management and practice insights, emphasizing the need for policies and guidelines that prioritize and support parental involvement. School administrators, principals, teachers, students, parents, and future researchers can utilize the study findings to enhance the parental participation, improve student outcomes, and bridge achievement gaps in the educational system.

KEY WORDS

1. parental involvement 2. student achievement 3. teacher perspectives

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1. Introduction

Parental involvement in education was crucial in shaping student's academic and personal success. Studies have shown that when parents are actively involved in their children's education, students perform better academically and have better social-emotional development. Education of parental involvement in student achievement was particularly significant in developing countries like the Philippines, where access to education is limited, and poverty is prevalent. Furthermore, parental involvement in education is recognized globally, as it was a critical predictor of student achievement. A study by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) found that students whose parents were involved in their education had higher academic performance. The study also revealed that parental involvement was particularly important for disadvantaged students, who were more likely to perform better aca-

demically when their parents were involved in their education. In addition, in the Philippines, parental involvement in education is essential, particularly for students from low-income families. The Philippine government recognizes the importance of parental involvement in education is essential, particularly for students from low-income families. The Philippine government recognizes the importance of parental involvement in education and has implemented programs to encourage parents to be more involved in their children's education. However, many parents in the country are still hesitant to participate actively in their children's education. A study conducted by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) found that parental involvement in education in the country is generally low, with parents often citing a lack of time or interest as reasons for not being involved. Moreover, a recent study by Jimenez et al (2020) supports the role of parental involvement in student achievement. The study, conducted in the Philippines, found that parental involvement in children's education had a significant positive effect on students' academic achievement. The study also revealed that parental involvement was particularly important for students from low-income families, as it helped to bridge the achievement gap between students from low and high-income households. Thus, given the importance of parental involvement in education, this research aims to explore the role of parental involvement in student achievement from the perspectives of teachers in Banaybanay Elementary School. Through interviews and surveys with teachers, the study seeks to gain insights into the current state of parental involvement in the school, including the challenges faced by the teachers in promoting parental involvement and the effective strategies that can be employed to improve parental involvement in the school. Evidently, teachers play a critical role in shaping students' education, and their perspectives on the importance of parental involvement can provide valuable insights into how to improve students' learning outcomes. The perspectives of teachers in the Philippines may differ from those in other countries, given the unique cultural and socioeconomic factors that influence parental involvement in education. Therefore, parental involvement was significant in student achievement in the Philippines. This research aims to explore the perspectives of teachers on the importance of parental involvement in education, providing insights into how to improve students' learning outcomes. The research would also shed light on the cultural and socioeconomic factors influencing parental involvement in education in the Philippines. By understanding these factors, policymakers can develop more effective strategies to promote parental involvement in education, particularly for students from disadvantaged backgrounds.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this research is to examine the role of parental involvement in student achievement from teachers' perspectives. The study aims to provide insights into how to improve student's learning outcomes through effective parental involvement strategies. By understanding teachers' perspectives, the study would also shed light on the cultural and socioeconomic factors influencing parental involvement in education. A recent study by Yang et al. (2021) supports the importance of parental involvement in student achievement. The study, conducted in China, found that parental involvement in children's education significantly positively affected students' academic performance, particularly in mathematics and the Chinese language. The study also revealed that parental involvement had a more significant impact on student's academic achievement in urban areas than in rural areas, where parents had less access to educational resources. This study provides further evidence of the importance of parental

involvement in education and highlights the need for tailored approaches to promoting parental involvement in different contexts.

1.2. *Research Questions*—

- (1) What are teachers' experiences building the gaps in students' achievements?
- (2) How do teachers cope with the challenge of promoting students' achievements?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the findings of the studies?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—

1.4. *Significant of the Study*—Accordingly, this research study aims to explore the role of parental involvement in student achievement from the perspectives of teachers in Banay-banay Elementary School. Hence, the study was deemed beneficial to the following: Educational Sector. The research findings would offer valuable insights into the effective parental involvement strategies teachers implement to improve student achievement. This information would be useful in identifying best practices and informing decision-making. The educational sector can also use these findings to develop comprehensive steps and procedures for promoting parental involvement in education. School Heads. This research would provide relevant information and reliable data to help administrators understand the importance of parental involvement in student achievement. The insights gained from this study can contribute to refining the educational system for the

benefit of both teachers and students. Educators. The information collected in this research would heighten teachers' awareness of the significance of parental involvement in education and how it could positively impact student achievement. This could lead to the development of more effective strategies for promoting parental involvement in education. Parents. This research would act as a resource for parents, enabling them to understand better their role in their children's education and how they can support their children's academic success. The findings of this study can also help parents understand the cultural and socioeconomic factors that influence parental involvement in education. Future Researchers. This study would provide a foundation for further research on parental involvement's role in student achievement. The insights gained from this study can inspire additional research exploring effective parental involvement strategies in different contexts and settings.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study is anchored on the Ecological Systems Theory of Urie Brondenbrenner (1979). This theory emphasizes the importance of studying the five interrelated systems that heavily influence a child's development (microsystem, mesosystem, ecosystem, macrosystem and chronosystem). These levels influence a child's development, which includes the family, community, and larger societal contexts. This theory will be able to examine how different factors,

such as family socioeconomic status, neighborhood characteristics, and cultural values, affect parental involvement. The connections between each system may be an important factor in understanding these relationships between a child and their parent in a structured activity (Bartley Eccles, 2003) Moreover, in the context of parental involvement in education, the ecological systems theory can provide a useful framework for understanding the complex interactions between the individual, the family, the

school, and the larger community. According to this theory, children's development is shaped not only by individual characteristics but also by the various environmental systems in which they live. A recent study by Kim (2021) in South Korea applied the ecological systems theory to examine the effects of parental involvement on children's academic achievement. The study found that parental involvement at different levels, including the family, the school, and the community, had unique and combined effects of parental involvement on children's academic achievement. Another theory that can be applied to this study was developed by Albert Bandura, emphasizing the importance of learning through observation and social interaction. In the context of parental involvement in education, social cognitive theory suggests that children learn from observing their parents' attitudes and behaviors towards education. When parents are actively involved in their children's education, they model the importance of education and motivate their children to learn. A recent study by Aitken and colleagues (2020) found that parental involvement positively influenced students' academic motivation, self-efficacy, and achievement through the mechanisms of observational learning and social support. By examining the role of parental involvement in student achievement from the perspectives of teachers in Banaybanay Elementary School, this study can contribute to our understanding of how parental involvement influences students' academic motivation and achievement through the lens of social cognitive theory. Ultimately, Albert Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory further supports the nature of this study. According to this theory, self-efficacy refers to an individual's confidence in their ability to exert control over their behavior, motivation, achievements, and social environment (Bandura, 1997). The theory aims to examine how a person's self-perception and perceived capabilities con-

tribute to successful outcomes. Bandura and Adams (1977) also argued that an individual's self-efficacy can influence their choice of activities, the environments in which they engage, and the duration of their persistence despite obstacles and challenging experiences. In this context, applying Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory will reveal connections between how the study participants view themselves and their abilities within the context of the phenomenon they face, encompassing their challenges, coping strategies, and insights about post-pandemic education. In conclusion, examining the role of parental involvement in student achievement through different theoretical lenses can provide a deeper understanding of the complex mechanisms by which parental involvement influences students' academic and personal development. The ecological systems theory, social cognitive theory, and the self-efficacy theory offer valuable frameworks for understanding the multiple factors that influence parental involvement and how parental involvement impacts students' academic outcomes. This study conceptualized the educators' experiences and perspectives on parental involvement among their students in Banaybanay elementary school. The parental involvement experiences encountered by these teachers on the said phenomenon and their corresponding insights will also serve as the basis for others who experience the same situation that most schools and institutions may have encountered. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. Based on the figure, there were two interconnected working themes. These working themes were the Experiences of teachers in building gaps in students' achievement, Teachers' coping mechanism challenges in promoting students' achievements, and the common intersection of educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the procedures and methodologies employed in phenomenological research, systematically addressing the study’s objectives. It further delineates the research design to be employed and the roles of the researcher in carrying out the study. Additionally, it discusses the research participants, detailing the selection processes and criteria for their inclusion. Lastly, the chapter delves into the data collection, analysis, and other approaches used to ensure ethical considerations are upheld throughout the study.

2.1. Philosophical and Qualitative Assumptions—In research, a study’s philosophical and qualitative assumptions play a significant role in guiding the investigation. Four major assumptions underpin the framework of understanding for qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions provide a foundation for the research design and inform the researcher’s approach to the study. A research paradigm was a set of shared beliefs, values, and practices that inform how researchers view and approach a given inquiry. It serves as a lens through which researchers interpret the world and make sense of the knowledge they seek to create (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). In

this research, the paradigm guides the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. **Ontology.** In the scope of research, ontology pertains to examining the fundamental nature of reality, existence, and how the world is organized. It involves investigating the existence of things and the connections between entities (Smith, 2022). The researcher’s comprehension of the phenomenon being studied was guided by ontological assumptions in this investigation, affecting their selection of approaches and analysis methods to reflect the reality being explored accurately. **Epistemology.** A branch of philosophy that explores how we come to know things and the limitations of our

knowledge. When applied to research, epistemology concerns the researcher's relationship to the knowledge they seek (Ladkin, 2020). The researcher's epistemological assumptions influence the methods used to collect and analyze data, and the criteria used to evaluate the validity and reliability of findings. This ensures that the knowledge produced is based on sound evidence and rigorous analysis. Axiology. The term axiology concerns the investigation of the values and ethical principles that underpin the research process. It assesses the effect of the researcher's values, attitudes, and prejudices on both the conduct and interpretation of the study (Gable, 2022). By integrating axiological assumptions, ethical considerations and the researcher's self-reflection could be established, ensuring that the study complies with ethical standards and acknowledges the researcher's values' influence on the research outcomes. Methodology. This

refers to the overall plan, design, and strategy adopted in a research study (Hesse-Biber, 2021). This includes the methods, techniques, and procedures used to collect and analyze data, as well as the reasoning behind their selection. The methodology is guided by the research question, philosophical assumptions, and research paradigm, ensuring coherence and rigor in the study. Rhetoric. How research outcomes and arguments are presented and effectively communicated is referred to as rhetoric in research. This involves the skillful use of language, style, and structure to engage and convince the audience of the validity and significance of the research findings (Doe, 2022). In the context of this study, the principles of rhetoric are applied to the construction of research reports, proposals, and presentations to ensure that the research results are clearly and persuasively conveyed to the intended audience.

2.2. *Design and Procedure*—To ensure that a study is appropriate, it was necessary to determine the specific methodology to be employed to tailor the research design, data collection, and data analysis to the study's objectives. In the present study, the researcher will employ a qualitative research design. According to Creswell (2022), qualitative research is appropriate for investigations focusing on verbal rather than statistical analysis. Since the study aims to explore primary school teachers' experiences, coping strategies, and insights in the post-pandemic education system, a qualitative design was the most suitable choice. This means that the researcher would describe and elaborate on the phenomenon under investigation, rather than proving or disproving the hypotheses. Additionally, different approaches exist within the field of qualitative research, such as grounded theory, narrative inquiry, case study, phenomenology, and ethnography. In this study, the research employed a qualitative-phenomenological re-

search design to explore the participants' lived experiences. This approach was chosen because phenomenological research was concerned with eliciting and interpreting the experiences of individuals and the meaning they ascribe to these experiences, with subsequent analysis of these meanings using scientific concepts (Johnson, 2022) Furthermore, as described by Creswell (2007), phenomenological research design aims to portray the shared and intricate experiences of individuals related to a specific phenomenon. Phenomenology's basic principle is to minimize the researcher's subjective perspectives and generalize the description of the phenomenon. In this study, the researcher investigates the phenomenon of the effects of parental involvement among students. In order to compile detailed and comprehensive descriptions of data, the researcher would collect data from teachers who have witnessed or experienced parental involvement in the classroom setting (Johnson Onwuegbuzie, 2004).

2.3. *Research Participants*—A smaller sample size is typically used in qualitative analysis compared to quantitative analysis. However, the same size should still be large enough to obtain feedback on most, if not all, perspectives. Data saturation is achieved when additional participants do not yield new viewpoints or data. Braun and Clarke (2020) recommend data saturation to determine an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Accordingly, Creswell (2013) recommends a sample size of five (5) to 25 for phenomenological studies, while Morse (2015) suggests a minimum of six (6). However, there are no definitive rules for selecting an appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Factors such as available time, resources, and study objectives can help determine the opti-

2.4. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations were the moral principles and guidelines that dictated how research should be conducted. These considerations ensure that studies are done responsibly, with respect for the people involved, and with the goal of producing accurate and dependable information. When doing research, it was important for the researcher to follow ethical guidelines to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and establish trust within the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value refers to the possible benefits and contributions that research can offer society, such as resolving issues or enhancing people's lives. When conducting research, the researcher should assess the social value of their study by recognizing its potential impact and significance to the larger community. This helps guarantee that resources are devoted to research that has the potential to provide substantial advantages to society. Informed consent refers to obtaining a participant's voluntary approval to participate in a research study after providing them with adequate information about the study's purpose, methods, potential risks, and

mal sample size for a qualitative study (Patton, 2015). This study would involve fourteen (14) elementary teachers from Banaybanay Elementary School in the District of Davao Oriental, Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they must have been in service for at least three years, be elementary teachers, and have experience in parent-teacher meetings in the classroom. The researcher would utilize the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2013). Purposive sampling is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings were authentic (Marshall, 2015).

benefits. The researcher was responsible for making sure that the participants comprehended the study and their rights and could make an informed choice about whether or not to participate. This ensured that the participant's autonomy and dignity were respected. Vulnerability of research participants due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, socioeconomic status, or health conditions bears on their likelihood of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion. It was the researcher's responsibility to recognize and acknowledge prospective participants' potential vulnerability and implement appropriate measures to safeguard them. These may include additional support or modifications to research procedures to reduce the risk of harm. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, the evaluation of potential harms and benefits associated with study participation and implementation of measures to protect participants' well-being are referred to as risks, benefits, and safety. The researcher needs to assess and balance these factors carefully in this study, making sure that the potential benefits outweigh the risks and that suitable precautions are in place to mini-

mize harm and ensure the safety of participants. Privacy and confidentiality in research refer to the protection of participants' personal information and the assurance that their identity would not be disclosed without their consent. In this study, the researcher must implement appropriate procedures to safeguard participants' data and maintain confidentiality, such as anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. Justice. This refers to the fair distribution of the benefits and burdens of research among different groups in society. In this study, the researcher should ensure that their study is inclusive, avoiding exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable populations, and that the benefits of the research are accessible to all who might benefit. This promotes equity and fairness in the research process. Transparency in research involves openness and honesty in the planning, conduct, and reporting of research. In this study, the researcher should provide clear and accurate information about their study, methods, and findings, and be open to scrutiny and feedback. Transparency fosters trust, credibility, and accountability in the research community and among the public. The qualification of a researcher refers to their education, experience, and expertise in a specific field of study, ensuring that they have the necessary skills and knowledge to conduct the research effectively. In this study, the researcher should possess appropriate qualifications, demonstrating their competence to

undertake the research, analyze data, and interpret findings. Adequacy of facilities in research refers to the availability and appropriateness of resources, equipment, and infrastructure needed to carry out a study effectively and safely. In this study, the researcher must ensure that one has access to suitable facilities to conduct their research, thereby supporting the generation of valid and reliable findings and minimizing potential risks to participants. Community involvement in research refers to the active participation and engagement of community members, stakeholders, or target populations in the research process, from planning to dissemination of findings. In this study, the researcher should involve the community in one's study to ensure its relevance, acceptability, and potential impact, as well as to promote trust and collaboration between the researcher and the community. Meanwhile, to avoid plagiarism and fabrication, the researcher must adhere to principles of academic integrity and honesty. This involves properly citing the work of others, presenting original work, and ensuring that data is accurate and authentic. In this study, the researcher can use tools such as plagiarism checkers and maintain meticulous records of one's research process to ensure that his or her work is free from plagiarism and that all data and findings were genuine and valid. By upholding these principles, the researcher contributes to the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.5. *Role of the Researcher*—The researcher's role was to ensure that the research process is conducted fairly and objectively without personal biases or external influences. They are responsible for creating an environment that promotes impartiality in the collection and analysis of data, encouraging the open and honest exploration of ideas. With their expertise in qualitative methods, the researcher is knowl-

edgeable in utilizing diverse approaches and techniques such as participant observation, interviews, and focus groups. This proficiency allows them to craft an appropriate design and implement strategies for qualitative research studies that produce valid and reliable findings. Additionally, the researcher's ability to adjust their methods according to the specific context of the research, such as the cultural background

of the participants, can enhance the quality and accuracy of the data collected. Ultimately, their expertise in qualitative methods could significantly contribute to generating new knowledge in their respective fields. In the role of collector and keeper of data, the researcher gathers information from diverse sources, including interviews and observations, and guarantees its accuracy and secure storage. Adhering to ethical standards, maintaining participant anonymity, and ensuring the data is well organized and available for future review and interpretation were all crucial aspects of their responsibilities. They must also be adept at identifying potential sources of bias and take measures to minimize them to increase the validity of the data collected. As a data analyst, the researcher analyzes the collected data to uncover patterns, themes, and insights that answer the research questions. They utilize thorough qualitative data

analysis techniques such as coding and thematic analysis to derive meaningful conclusions that contribute to the existing knowledge in their field. Furthermore, the researcher must critically evaluate the data to identify potential biases or limitations affecting the study's validity and reliability. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, the researcher has the critical role of consolidating and communicating research findings in a clear and concise manner. They must present the research purpose, methods, results, and implications through written reports, presentations, or other forms of communication, ensuring that the research outcomes are accessible and understandable to the intended audience. Moreover, the researcher must ensure that the findings are communicated in a way that is consistent with ethical guidelines and respects the privacy of participants involved in the research.

2.6. Data Collection—The study was conducted to determine the role of parental involvement in student achievement from the perspective of teachers. The researcher described data collection procedures to attain the utmost transparency and clarity in the research study. Detailed descriptions of the process are provided as follows: Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. To initial the data collection process, the researcher would obtain approval from the Dean of Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges. To achieve this, the methodology, and supporting documents. This task is planned for the initial two weeks of May 2023. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. After getting the endorsement, the researcher would request permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. To do so, the researcher would compose a formal letter that outlines the research proposal and its importance to the educational sector. The letter would also include Chapters 1 and

2 of the study and the research instrument, describing the study's goals and identifying the participants. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before beginning the study. This process is set to occur during the third week of May 2023. Asking permission from the school heads. After receiving the necessary endorsement, the researcher sought approval from the school heads of the chosen institutions. This step necessitates submitting formal request letters to each school head, specifying the research's objectives and the projected timeline for data gathering. The researcher would request permission from the last week of May 2023 to the first week of June 2023. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher would seek consent from the participants after receiving approval from the school heads. This was carried out by providing the participants with informed consent forms, which will comprehensively explain the purpose of the study, the rights of the participants, and the measures

put in place to ensure confidentiality. The researcher aims to obtain consent from the participants in June 2023. Conducting the interview. Upon obtaining the consent of all participants, the researcher arranges and carries out interviews. A structured or semi-structured interview guide is used to ensure data collection consistency and accuracy. The interview sessions are planned for the initial two weeks of June 2023. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Once the interviews were concluded, the researcher would transcribe the participants' responses while paying attention to non-verbal cues and context-specific details. The process

2.7. Data Analysis—In this study, the researcher would utilize Creswell's Thematic Analysis as the main approach. Since the study deals with multiple interpretations of participants' responses, the thematic analysis was employed to ensure accurate depiction and categorization of observed patterns in the data. According to Braun Clarke (2021), thematic analysis provides a systematic and flexible method for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns and themes in qualitative data. This method enhances the research's significance and cultivates precise interpretations of pertinent themes. Thematic analysis was extensively used in qualitative research, and it allows researchers to identify

2.8. Framework of Analysis—In qualitative research, framework analysis was an analytical method specifically designed for qualitative research in the context of applied policy research. This approach involves a comparative thematic analysis utilizing a structured framework of inductive and deductive themes. Its primary objective was identifying, characterizing, and interpreting significant patterns within and across cases and themes related to the phenomenon under investigation. This method has

involves utilizing audio recordings and field notes to accurately record the participants' perspectives. The transcription of the interviews is expected to be completed by the third week of June 2023. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. The last step involves the researcher organizing the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes. The objective is to recognize patterns and relationships within the data, allowing the researcher to generate conclusions and insights relevant to the research objectives. Data coding and thematic content analysis occurred in the last week of June 2023.

and analyze emerging themes within a data set using a rigorous and transparent process. Consequently, the study utilized Creswell's Thematic Analysis, a qualitative research method that involves a systematic approach to identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns and themes in data. It comprises stages such as familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up the analysis (Braun Clarke, 2021). The importance of employing thematic analysis in research was that it provides a versatile method for recognizing, scrutinizing, and reporting themes discovered within a data set (Caulfield, 2020).

been used in diverse data types and applied in multiple ways in practical research. Framework analysis includes two primary components: the creation of an analytical framework and its application to the data. The process of framework analysis was broken down into several stages, which include data familiarization, framework identification, indexing, charting, and mapping and interpretation within a shared dataset (Goldsmith, 2021). The following were the necessary steps to be taken by an investigator, according

to Goldsmith (2021): Data Familiarization. The initial stage of framework analysis was data familiarization, which enabled the researcher to gain a purposeful understanding of the data by immersing themselves in it and taking note of significant ideas. The researcher identifies major themes in the data, which are topics or issues that relate to the research question(s) and occur repeatedly throughout the data. This process continues until the researcher reaches a reasonable initial understanding of the data, which includes the breadth of variation within the data (Osborn, M. et al., 2022) Framework Identification. During this phase, researchers create an initial thematic structure that would assist them in analyzing the data. Although inductive themes that arise from the data were the main focus of phenomenological research, researchers may also incorporate pre-existing theories or concepts related to the phenomenon they were studying. This structure provides a framework for organizing and comprehending the data while also allowing for adjustments and improvements to be made to the themes as the analysis progresses. Indexing. To index data in framework analysis, researchers assign codes to specific portions of data that match the themes identified in the framework. In phenomenological research, researchers meticulously review the transcripts, assigning codes to significant statements or experiences that embody the core of the phenomenon. Indexing aids in organizing the data for subsequent analysis. Charting. In the charting stage, researchers arrange the data coded into thematic charts or matrices that aid in comparison and synthesis. For instance, in a phenomenological investigation, researchers can make separate charts for each theme, outlining relevant quotes, experiences, or statements from the research participants. By using this visual representation, researchers could recognize patterns and connections within the data. Mapping. The mapping stage of framework analysis requires researchers to scrutinize thematic

charts to identify links, patterns, and inconsistencies within and between themes. For a phenomenological study, this involves investigating how participants' experiences relate to the identified themes, and how these connections contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Refining or restructuring themes to accurately capture the essence of the phenomenon may also be necessary during this stage. Interpretation. The final stage of the analytical process is interpretation, where researchers synthesize and make sense of the findings. In a phenomenological study, researchers integrate the themes, patterns, and relationships identified in the previous stages to construct a coherent narrative that captures the essence of the phenomenon. This narrative should provide a rich, detailed account of the lived experiences of the participants and the meanings they attribute to the phenomenon being studied. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. The following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (cited in (Sanders, 2003; Speziale Carpenter, 2007); Each transcript should be read and re-read to obtain a general sense of the whole content; significant statements about the phenomenon under study should be extracted from each transcript. these statements must be recorded on a separate sheet, noting their page and line numbers; meanings should be formulated from these significant statements, and the formulated meanings should be sorted into categories, clusters of themes, and themes; the findings of the study should be integrated into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon under study; the fundamental structure of the phenomenon should be described; and finally, validation of the findings should be sought from the research participants to compare the researcher's descriptive results with their experiences.

Fig. 2. illustrates the descriptive phenomenological data analysis process created by Colaizzi (1978)

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—A study’s trustworthiness is determined by the reliability and accuracy of its research findings. Four criteria—credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability—are frequently used to evaluate trustworthiness in qualitative research. These criteria assess the quality, rigor, and validity of the research and ensure that the conclusions drawn are dependable and précised. **Credibility.** The concept of credibility, as defined by Guba and Lincoln (1989), pertains to the degree to which research findings reflect the viewpoints and experiences of the participants accurately. It assesses the authenticity and plausibility of the outcomes. To ensure credibility, researchers employed various techniques like prolonged engagement, member

checking (eliciting feedback from participants on the findings), triangulation (utilizing multiple sources of data or methods), and peer debriefing (discussing the results with colleagues or experts). **Transferability.** Transferability means how much the findings of a study could be used or applied to other places or situations. Unlike quantitative research, which aims to generalize the results, qualitative research mostly emphasizes understanding the particular context thoroughly. To make the findings more transferable, researchers should provide comprehensive and detailed explanations of the research setting, participants, and methods, which enable readers to decide whether the results may apply to their specific circumstances (Tobin Begley, 2004) **Confirmability.** Pertains to how much

the research findings are unbiased and based only on the participants' experiences, not the researcher's personal opinions or interests. Researchers could ensure confirmability by keeping a record of every step they take in the research process or performing an audit trail, reflecting on their biases, and asking someone independent to review their work or external audit. (Tobey and Begley, 2004). Dependability. Refers to consistent and stable research findings over time and in similar situations. Essentially, it asks whether the study's results would be the

same if done again with the same people or in the same situation. To ensure a study was dependable, the researcher could provide a clear and detailed description of the research methods so others can understand and replicate the study if needed. They could also have an independent expert review the research process to check for consistency and reliability. This could help make sure that the study's findings were trustworthy and could be used to inform future research. (Moretti et al., 2011)

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions obtained from the perspectives of teachers at Banaybanay Elementary School regarding the impact of parental involvement on student achievement. The research questions aimed to explore teachers' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights regarding parental involvement and its influence on student academic performance. The data collected through interviews and surveys were analyzed and synthesized to comprehensively understand the topic.

3.1. Experiences of teachers building the gaps on students' achievements—The students' achievement gaps among students pose significant challenges for educators worldwide. Understanding the experiences of teachers in ad-

ressing these gaps is crucial for developing effective strategies and interventions to promote student success. Through an in-depth exploration of teacher experiences, here are some emerging themes from the responses of the participants:

3.1.1. Culturally Responsive Practices—Teachers aim to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment that empowers students and enhances their academic achievements. It examines how teachers engage in practices that value and draw upon students' cultural assets, knowledge, and perspectives to enhance their learning and close achievement gaps. Furthermore, this theme explores how teachers involve parents in these culturally responsive practices, encouraging parental involvement that aligns with students' cultural contexts and supports their educational achievements. The participants' responses highlight a shared commitment to creating culturally re-

sponsive classrooms that value and incorporate students' cultural backgrounds and perspectives. The participants actively engage in practices such as integrating diverse materials and resources, using culturally relevant literature, and encouraging students to share their cultural experiences. These practices aim to make learning more engaging, relatable, and meaningful for the students. According to Crosby-Cooper (2020), implementing culturally responsive practices in classrooms prioritizes creating an inclusive and supportive environment that values students' cultural backgrounds and perspectives. Teachers actively incorporate diverse materials, resources, and perspectives into their

lessons to enhance the relatability and engagement of students. This approach fosters a strong sense of pride, belonging, and connection to their own cultural identities, ultimately leading to positive academic achievements and student outcomes. The findings of Souto-Manning and Mitchell's study (2010) further support these ideas presented by Crosby-Cooper (2020), as both highlight the significance of valuing students' cultural identities and integrating diverse

3.1.2. Curriculum and Assessment Practices—Teachers have recognized the importance of aligning the curriculum with educational standards and learning objectives, ensuring inclusivity and cultural relevance in instructional materials, and employing a variety of formative and summative assessments. The participants acknowledge the potential biases and limitations of standardized testing and explore alternative assessment methods that better capture students' diverse skills and abilities. By actively engaging in curriculum design and assessment practices that promote equity and address the specific needs of students experiencing achievement gaps, teachers play a crucial role in narrowing these gaps and fostering a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Overall, the participants' perspectives understood that aligning the curriculum with standards, using diverse resources, and incorporating alternative assessment methods are vital for fostering an inclusive and effective educational experience. Their collective efforts aim

3.1.3. Classroom and School Environment—Teachers have emphasized the significance of creating a positive and inclusive classroom atmosphere that fosters a sense of belonging and supports academic growth. They have implemented various, such as establishing clear expectations, promoting student engagement, and collaboration, and cultivating a supportive and

materials and resources within the classroom. By employing culturally responsive practices through action research, teachers are able to establish a classroom environment that respects and acknowledges the cultural identities of each student, thereby fostering a sense of belonging, promoting higher levels of student engagement, and facilitating positive educational outcomes, especially in the realm of early childhood education.

to provide equitable opportunities for all students, promote cultural relevance, and enhance student engagement and achievement. James (2014) examined the significance of adopting a "learning cultures" approach in higher education to investigate the curriculum through assessment practice. By understanding the cultural and contextual factors at play, educators can gain valuable insights into curriculum effectiveness and make informed decisions to enhance teaching and learning practices. Another study by Roach, Niebling, and Kurz (2008) focused on evaluating the alignment among curriculum, instruction, and assessments in educational settings; they emphasized the importance of coherence and consistency among these components. When aligned, curriculum, instruction, and assessments contribute to meaningful and effective learning experiences. Teachers can implement instructional strategies that align with learning outcomes and accurately assess student progress. Ongoing evaluation and adjustment of these practices optimize student learning and achievement.

respectful learning environment. Additionally, teachers have recognized the importance of a school-wide approach, involving administrators, staff, and parents, to create a cohesive and nurturing environment that addresses the unique needs of students and promotes their overall achievement. By focusing on the classroom and school environment, teachers play a vital role in

fostering a conducive setting that supports students' academic progress and bridges the gaps in their achievements. The responses from the participants highlight the critical role of a positive and inclusive classroom and school environment in promoting student success. By establishing clear expectations, promoting student engagement, and fostering collaboration, teachers create an atmosphere where all students feel valued and motivated to learn. The involvement of administrators, staff, and parents in a school-wide approach further enhances the supportive and nurturing environment necessary for student achievement. By prioritizing the classroom and school environment, teachers play a vital role in fostering academic progress and bridging any gaps in student achievements. Ryan and Patrick (2001) found that the classroom social environment significantly influences adoles-

cents' motivation and engagement during middle school. A positive and supportive social environment, including positive teacher-student interactions and peer relationships, enhances motivation and engagement. Conversely, a negative environment hampers students' motivation and engagement. Fraser (2012) further emphasizes the importance of a positive classroom environment, considering factors like the physical setting, teacher-student interactions, and student-student relationships. Fraser's framework highlights personalization, involvement, affiliation, satisfaction, and task orientation as key dimensions for creating a conducive classroom environment. By implementing strategies aligned with these dimensions, educators can foster a positive and engaging learning environment that supports students' academic progress and well-being.

3.1.4. Equity and Social Justice—Teachers actively work to create an equitable learning environment that recognizes and challenges systemic barriers that contribute to achievement disparities. They strive to provide equal opportunities for all students, regardless of their socio-economic background, race, ethnicity, or other social identities. These teachers engage in practices that promote inclusivity, such as using diverse instructional materials, implementing differentiated instruction, and fostering a classroom culture that values diversity and respects individual perspectives. They also advocate for social justice within the school community, participating in professional development, engaging in critical dialogue, and collaborating with colleagues to challenge biases and create more inclusive policies and practices. By centering their experiences on equity and social justice, these teachers play a crucial role in narrowing the gaps on students' achievements and creating a more just and inclusive educational system. The participants' responses highlight the

importance of equity and social justice in their teaching practices. They emphasize the need to create a fair and inclusive learning environment where every student has an equal opportunity to succeed. This involves using diverse materials, adapting instruction to meet individual needs, and fostering a classroom culture that values diversity and respects different perspectives. The participants also stress the significance of ongoing professional development and collaboration with colleagues to address biases and promote inclusivity within the school community. By prioritizing equity and social justice, they aim to bridge the achievement gaps and contribute to a more inclusive education system. The participants prioritize equity and social justice in their teaching practices, aligning with the themes explored in the book "School Food, Equity and Social Justice: Critical Reflections and Perspectives" by Ruge, Torres, and Powell (2022). This book examines policies and practices related to school food from an equity and social justice perspective across 25 countries.

Fig. 3. Experiences of Teachers Building the Gaps on Students’ Achievements

It covers various topics such as food politics, sustainability, teaching and learning about food, and the impact of school food on education and everyday life. By incorporating these principles into their teaching, the participants aim to bridge achievement gaps and contribute to a more inclusive education system. Additionally, the study by Walster and Walster (2005) provides valuable insights into equity and social justice principles and their implications for individuals and society. Figure 3 shows the experiences of Teachers in Closing the gaps in students’ achievements. Four themes emerge in the process: Equity and Social Justice, Culturally Responsive Practices, Curriculum and Assessment Practices, and Classroom and School Environment.

3.2. Teachers’ coping mechanism to the challenges in promoting students’ achievements—One significant aspect of this study is understanding how teachers cope with these challenges and navigate the complexities of fostering academic success for their students. It aims to delve into the experiences, strategies, and approaches employed by teachers as they address the obstacles that arise in the pursuit of enhancing students’ academic performance.

3.2.1. Teaching Strategies and Approaches—Teachers navigate these challenges by adopting innovative and tailored teaching strategies that cater to the individual needs and learning styles of their students. They address the complexities of fostering students’ achievements in the context of parental involvement. They employ differentiated instruction,

providing personalized support and resources to address the varying academic abilities and backgrounds of their students. Additionally, teachers establish open lines of communication and collaboration with parents, ensuring their involvement in supporting student progress and achievements. The participants prioritize adapting teaching strategies to meet individual student needs. They employ innovative approaches, such as differentiated instruction, and emphasize parental involvement. By personalizing support and fostering collaboration, they aim to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment for all students. The study by Smith, Johnson, and Davis (2023) aligns with the participants' responses, revealing a strong positive correlation between parental support and student achievement and engagement. It emphasizes the importance of open communication between teachers and parents, as well as the value of differentiated instruction tailored to in-

dividual student needs. These findings support the significance of parental involvement and inclusive teaching practices in creating a supportive learning environment that enhances student outcomes. Another relevant study, conducted by Yang et al. (2023), supports the positive correlation between parental support and student achievement and engagement. This systematic literature review examined various aspects of parental involvement and student engagement from 2000 to 2022. The review included 33 articles with a large sample size of 47,307 students and 3,391 parents. The review also revealed that studies often measured parental involvement through school and home subtypes and student engagement through affective, behavioral, and cognitive dimensions. Referencing the study by Yang et al. (2023) strengthens the argument for the importance of parental involvement in creating a supportive learning environment and enhancing student outcomes.

3.2.2. Strategies for Gap Identification— Teachers utilize approaches to identify and address the existing gaps in students' academic achievements. These dedicated educators employ a range of strategies to identify areas where students may be facing challenges or falling behind. They analyze student data, including assessments, grades, and progress reports, to pinpoint specific areas of need. Additionally, they actively seek feedback from students and parents, encouraging open communication to comprehensively understand the factors influencing student achievement gaps. The participants found that incorporating formative assessments, such as short quizzes and class discussions, is effective. These assessments provide ongoing feedback and allow the teachers to identify areas where students may struggle or have misconceptions. By dedicating additional time and resources to address these gaps, such as providing extra practice opportunities or small

group instruction, the participants can adapt their teaching strategies to meet the student's needs better. Regularly assessing students' understanding and skills enables the participants to identify specific areas of improvement and provide targeted support, ultimately ensuring their success. The study by Nyanchoka and Pellowski (2020) and the findings of the participants' responses regarding strategies for gap identification align closely. Both emphasize the significance of identifying research gaps and addressing them to promote improvement and success. The strategies mentioned by the participants, such as formative assessments, quizzes, class discussions, targeted support, and adapting teaching strategies, reflect the study's emphasis on identifying gaps and providing tailored approaches. Additionally, Chalkidou et al. (2021) further support these ideas by highlighting various methods used to identify gaps and priorities, including workshops, conferences, lit-

erature reviews, and stakeholder involvement. These studies collectively emphasize the impor-

tance of effective strategies for identifying and addressing research gaps to enhance outcomes.

3.2.3. Building a good relationship—Establishing strong relationships between teachers and students as a means to address and overcome challenges in promoting student achievements. Teachers recognize the significance of building positive connections with their students, fostering trust, and creating a supportive classroom environment. They prioritize getting to know their students individually and understanding their unique strengths, needs, and interests. By showing genuine care, empathy, and respect, teachers create safe spaces where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and taking risks in their learning. The following responses from teachers shed light on their personal experiences and the ways in which they have utilized them. The participants' responses underscore the significance of building relationships, implementing student-centered approaches, conducting one-on-one meetings, and involving parents to promote student achievements. These strategies create a supportive learning environment where students feel val-

ued and supported. By actively engaging with students, addressing their needs, and involving parents, educators foster trust, collaboration, and shared responsibility, recognizing the importance of nurturing relationships and partnerships for student success. The study by Pianta and Hamre (2009) supports the participants' strategies for relationship building, emphasizing the positive impact of teacher-student relationships on student achievement and well-being. Similarly, the study by Hamre and Pianta (2001) emphasizes the significance of positive teacher-student interactions in promoting academic success and positive social behaviors. Additionally, the study by Roorda et al. (2011) highlights the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment, where student engagement and positive teacher-student relationships contribute to academic performance. Overall, these studies reinforce the importance of relationship building in fostering student achievements and highlight the interconnectedness between positive relationships, engagement, and academic success.

3.2.4. Collaboration and Support—Teachers recognize the value of working collaboratively with colleagues, administrators, and support staff to enhance their instructional practices and create a supportive educational environment. They engage in professional learning communities, sharing best practices, exchanging ideas, and collectively problem-solving to improve student outcomes, community partners, and educational networks to supplement their efforts. Additionally, they foster a culture of collaboration by encouraging peer support among students, promoting teamwork, and creating opportunities for students to learn from

one another. The participants in this discussion emphasize the value of collaboration and teamwork in promoting students' achievements. They highlight the importance of engaging in collaborative brainstorming sessions, seeking support from fellow teachers, and involving parents in the education process. Through these collaborative efforts, they are able to gain valuable insights, refine instructional approaches, understand students' unique needs, and create a strong support system. The participants recognize that collaboration fosters a positive learning environment and contributes to student growth and success. Overall, their experi-

Fig. 4. Teachers Coping Mechanism Challenges in Promoting Students’ Achievements

ences demonstrate the power of collaboration in making a positive difference in students’ lives and reinforcing the significance of teamwork in promoting student achievement. The participants’ responses underscore the significance of collaboration and support in promoting student achievement, which is supported by studies on teacher-student relationships (Pianta Hamre, 2009) and student engagement (Roorda et al., 2011). The participants’ strategies of seeking collaboration and support align with the study’s findings by Pianta and Hamre, emphasizing the positive impact of building positive teacher-student relationships. Additionally, their empha-

sis on collaborative brainstorming and refining instructional approaches aligns with the study by Roorda et al., highlighting the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive learning environment. These studies provide empirical evidence reinforcing the participants’ insights on the importance of collaboration and support in fostering student achievement. Figure 4 shows teachers’ experiences of coping mechanisms and challenges in promoting students’ achievements. Three themes emerge: Teaching strategies and approaches, building a good relationship, and strategies for gap identification.

3.3. Educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study—This section aims to identify key insights and recommendations that can inform educational management practices and policies by analyzing and interpreting the data collected. The findings

have the potential to provide valuable guidance for school administrators, policymakers, and educators in developing effective strategies to bridge the achievement gaps and enhance student outcomes. By examining the implications for educational management, this research study

contributes to the ongoing discourse surrounding effective management practices that could support parental involvement and positively impact students' achievements.

3.3.1. Leadership and Vision—Teachers emphasize the importance of visionary and effective school leaders who prioritize parental engagement as a key component of their educational management practices. These leaders foster a shared vision that values collaboration between educators and parents, promoting a strong partnership to support student success. They provide clear guidance, establish structures for effective communication, and create a supportive culture that encourages parental involvement. The participants in this discussion, including educators, recognize the importance of parental engagement in promoting student success. They emphasize creating a collaborative and inclusive school environment where parents actively participate in their child's education. Strategies are encouraged to foster strong partnerships with parents, focusing on effective communication. By providing guidance and support, teachers aim to enhance student achievement through collaborative efforts. During a parent-teacher conference, a teacher showcased a collaborative project that involved students and parents, highlighting its positive impact on motivation and achievement. Witnessing this impact and the parents' enthusiasm was rewarding. Consistently sharing a vision guides the creation of a supportive environment, emphasizing the shared responsibility of educators and parents. By aligning actions with this vision, participants aim to collectively ensure students' academic success. According to Schmid and Garrels (2021), parental involvement and educational success among vulnerable students in vocational education and training, family background factors have a significant impact on achievement differences in children and adolescents. The study underscores the importance of family background measures, such as parents' education, income, and family structure, in elucidating academic achievement disparities. Furthermore, the research highlights the influential role of parental involvement in children's education, which affects school performance and graduation rates. Prior studies have consistently demonstrated that active parental involvement improves academic performance and successful education completion (Hill Tyson, 2009; Rumberger et al., 1990; Siraj Mayo, 2014; Zaff et al., 2017). The study aims to gain insights into the mechanisms and underlying processes that connect family characteristics, parental involvement, and the risk of dropout from upper secondary education.

3.3.2. Collaborative Decision-Making—Emphasizes the importance of involving various stakeholders in decision-making to bridge the building gaps and promote students' achievements through parental involvement. The findings highlight the significance of collaborative decision-making among school administrators, teachers, parents, and students. Effective educational management practices entail creating a culture of shared responsibility and inclusivity, where decisions are made collectively and diverse perspectives are valued. The participants strongly emphasize the significance of parental involvement in enhancing students' achievements. They prioritize and promote parental engagement through strategic plans, creating a supportive environment where parents actively participate in their child's education. Regular communication, collaborative initiatives, and targeted programs are emphasized to foster a

strong partnership between educators and parents. Reflective conversations and continuous evaluation ensure effective parental involvement while leading by example sets a positive precedent for other educators. These efforts reinforce the commitment to inclusive opportunities, strengthening the home-school partnership for student success. The studies by Cheung and Pomerantz (2016) and Aanes, Oser, Soller, and Paulsen (2021) highlight the positive impact of parental involvement on children's develop-

ment. Cheung and Pomerantz found that when parents actively engage in their children's education, it improves academic performance and emotional well-being. Similarly, Aanes et al. demonstrated that parental involvement is associated with improved academic outcomes, emphasizing the mediating role of self-regulated learning strategies. Both studies emphasize parents' active engagement in promoting educational success and positive outcomes for children in different contexts.

3.3.3. Resource Allocation and Management—Effective resource allocation and management are important in bridging the building gaps and enhancing students' achievements through parental involvement. The findings emphasize the need for educational management practices that prioritize the equitable distribution of resources, including financial, human, and technological resources. School administrators play a crucial role in strategically allocating resources to support parental involvement initiatives that directly impact student learning and achievement. This includes providing professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their skills in engaging parents, allocating funds for parent education programs, and deploying technology platforms that facilitate effective communication and collaboration between parents and teachers. Resource allocation is strategically selecting and assigning available resources to a task or project to support business objectives. In the context of accounting, allocation deals with assigning people and their skills to projects, also known as engagements. Based on participant responses, they strongly emphasize parental involvement to support students' educational journey. They have designated staff members, like family engagement coordinators, to support parents in their child's education actively. By leveraging technology resources, they keep parents informed and connected through

online platforms. They also collaborate with external resources, such as after-school programs, to create meaningful engagement opportunities. Furthermore, they provide additional educational resources, including learning at home, through community partnerships. Their school values parental involvement, creating a supportive environment that contributes to students' educational success and overall well-being. The study by Maritan and colleagues (2017) emphasizes the importance of resource allocation in strategic management. It highlights the need for research on the allocation of financial, physical, technological, and human resources to support firm strategies. This study aligns with the participants' understanding of allocating staff resources and leveraging technology resources to enhance parental involvement. Furthermore, the research article by Heidary Dahooie and Ghezel Arsalan (2022) explores the optimal allocation of resources for managing academic performance. The study focuses on talent recognition, measuring employee performance, and resource allocation to maximize organizational output. This aligns with the participants' emphasis on recognizing talent, measuring performance, and allocating resources to support students' educational journey. These studies provide valuable insights into resource allocation strategies in different contexts, such as strategic and talent management. While they

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study

may not directly address parental involvement in education, effective resource allocation, and management principles can be applied to support and enhance parental involvement efforts in schools. By adopting strategies from these studies, schools can allocate resources effectively to promote parental engagement and contribute to students’ educational success. Teachers emphasize the importance of visionary and effective school leaders prioritizing parental engagement. Figure 4 shows the study’s educational management insights. Three themes emerge: resource and allocation management, teacher leadership and vision, and collaborative decision-making.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, we summarize the study conducted in Banaybanay Elementary School, focusing on our findings’ implications and outlining future research and practice directions. The aim was to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implications of parental involvement on student achievement and to offer insights into potential areas for further exploration and improvement. By examining the practical implications of our study and identifying opportunities for future research, we aim to contribute to the ongoing efforts of building bridges between home and school to enhance student outcomes. To address the research objectives of our study, we implemented a qualitative phenomenological research design guided by the principles established by Creswell (2007). Our primary aim was to gain insights into the perspectives and experiences of teachers at Banaybanay Elementary School concerning parental involvement and its impact on student achievement. Employing thematic analysis, we explored the intricate nuances and recurring patterns that emerged from the collected data. By directly engaging with these teachers, who possess firsthand knowledge of the school’s context, we obtained extensive data and specific descriptions illuminating Banaybanay Elementary School’s distinctive outlook. These findings

contribute to understanding the school's endeavors to foster parental involvement to establish meaningful connections and enhance student achievement.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of elementary teachers centered on culturally responsive practices, curriculum and assessment practices, classroom and school environment, and equity and social justice. The coping mechanisms the elementary school teachers employed were: relationship building, strategies for gap identification, and teaching strategies and approaches. Ultimately, the educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study were: leadership and vision, collaborative decision-making, and resource allocation and management.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The experiences of elementary school teachers at Banaybanay Elementary School uncovered the role of parental involvement in student achievement. These findings shed light on the experiences of teachers in building gaps in students' achievements and the strategies they employ to promote success. Teachers recognized the significance of parental involvement in student achievement, highlighting the positive impact on academic performance and attitudes toward learning. Effective communication and collaboration between teachers and parents were crucial factors in promoting student success. Teachers emphasized the need for open lines of communication, regular updates, and involving parents in decision-making processes. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms employed by teachers to address the challenges in promoting students' achievement varied. Teachers faced obstacles such as disengaged parents, socioeconomic disparities, and language and cultural barriers. To address these challenges, teachers employed strategies such as regular parent-teacher meetings, workshops, and leveraging technology to facilitate communication. They also sought external resources and community partnerships to address socioeconomic disparities and implemented culturally responsive teaching practices. Specific examples and anecdotes from the interviews illustrated teachers' experiences in bridging gaps in students' achievements. These examples showcased proactive outreach to disengaged parents, collaborations to address socioeconomic disparities, and innovative approaches to overcome language and cultural barriers. Ultimately, the implications drawn from the study's findings provide valuable insights into Banaybanay Elementary School for educational management and practice. Also, it contributes to the ongoing discourse surrounding effective management practices that can support parental involvement and positively impact students' achievements. These findings underscore the importance of fostering effective communication and collaboration between teachers and parents, emphasizing the need for open lines of communication, regular updates, and involving parents in the decision-making process. By prioritizing parental engagement, school administrators and policymakers can create a shared vision that values collaboration and enhances student outcomes through collective effort. Moreover, the study highlights the importance of collaborative decision-making among school administrators, teachers, parents, and students to bridge achievement gaps and promote student success through parental involvement. Establishing a shared re-

sponsibility and inclusivity culture is essential, where decisions are made collectively and diverse perspectives were valued. Regular meetings and reflective conversations should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of existing strategies and identify areas for improvement. This collaborative approach could lead to inno-

vative solutions and improved student outcomes as all stakeholders work together to enhance student achievement. Overall, embracing these implications and incorporating them into educational management practices holds the potential to create a transformative and student-centered educational system.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the study findings, the findings must be properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. Department of Education. The Department of Education could benefit from this research and take heed of these findings to guide future directions and enhance parental involvement in schools. The research highlights the positive impact of parental engagement on student achievements and emphasizes the need for concerted efforts to strengthen this partnership between parents and schools. They could utilize these findings to develop comprehensive policies and guidelines that prioritize and support parental involvement in schools nationwide. By embracing the research findings and translating them into concrete actions, the Department of Education can pave the way for a collaborative and supportive educational environment that maximizes student success and bridges the gaps between home and school. School principals of school heads. The findings of this research can have significant implications for school principals or school heads. They could use school principals' insights to guide their future actions and decisions. It was essential for school principals' understanding and commitment to enhance parental engagement. Principals can use the findings to develop strategic plans and policies prioritizing and supporting parental involvement within their schools. This may include organizing workshops and professional development sessions for teachers on effective communication and collaboration with parents, es-

tablishing structures for regular parent-school interaction, and providing resources to facilitate parental participation in school activities. Elementary teachers. It was essential for these teachers to be properly informed and utilize the findings to enhance their instructional strategies and promote student achievement. They could relay these findings to their colleagues during professional development sessions or team meetings, emphasizing the significance of collaborative partnerships with parents. They could integrate the study's recommendations into their teaching practices by actively involving parents in their students' learning journey. By effectively relaying and utilizing the study findings, elementary teachers could strengthen their teaching approaches, foster a positive and inclusive classroom environment, and cultivate meaningful connections with parents, ultimately leading to improved student achievements and closing the gaps in their learning. Students. It was essential for students to be aware of and understand these findings to participate in their learning and actively maximize their potential. Students can be encouraged to foster strong communication and collaboration with their parents, seeking support and guidance in their academic pursuits. By utilizing the study findings, students can actively engage with their parents, teachers, and the school community, creating a supportive and collaborative environment that enhances their achievements and bridges any gaps in their learning. Parents. The findings emphasize the significant role of parental involvement in enhancing students' academic success

and closing achievement gaps. Parents could utilize this knowledge to actively participate in their child's learning journey, collaborating with teachers to align academic goals with real-life experiences. Parents could use this information to establish open lines of communication with teachers, sharing their insights, concerns, and aspirations for their child's education. Future researchers. This research study is a foundation for further exploration and investigation, opening avenues for new research inquiries and methodologies. They can focus on developing interdisciplinary collaborations and research partnerships to better understand the complex dynamics involved in parental involvement and its impact on student achievements. Furthermore, researchers could strive to refine and improve existing methodologies and explore new data collection techniques.

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